

THE IMPACT OF INFLATION ON HOUSE PRICES IN SOUTH AFRICA: EFFECTS OF COVID-19

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This study investigates the impact of inflation on house prices in South Africa, with a particular focus on the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. The research aims to elucidate the nature of the relationship between inflation and housing, and to determine how the pandemic has influenced this dynamic. Utilising monthly data from January 2010 to April 2022, the study employs Johansen cointegration and Granger causality tests to assess long-term and causal relationships, respectively. The findings confirm a positive long-term relationship between house prices and inflation, indicating that housing serves as an effective hedge against inflation. However, the results also reveal structural breaks in this relationship, with significant changes observed during the COVID-19 period. The Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) highlights short-run adjustments and the speed of return to equilibrium. This study provides valuable insights for investors and policymakers, demonstrating the resilience of housing investments during economic disruptions and underscoring the importance of considering regional and temporal factors in real estate investment strategies.

Keywords: Covid-19, granger causality test, house prices, inflation, Johansen cointegration, South Africa

INTRODUCTION

Real estate as an inflation hedge

Inflation is crucial for long-term investors. Nguyen (2023) notes that investors prefer assets like gold, oil, and real estate based on inflation forecasts. Real estate prices rise with inflation due to CPI-linked leases and higher construction costs, impacting housing supply (Akal, 2023). Fama and Schwert (1977) found that privately held residential real estate effectively hedges against both expected and unexpected inflation. Stevenson (2000) confirmed that housing and inflation in the UK are cointegrated, indicating that residential property acts as a long-term inflation hedge. Lee (2013) suggests inflation uncertainty prompts housing investment, while Lee (2021) identified a short-term positive relationship.

Empirical evidence from different regions

Hin Li and Lin Ge (2008) used ARIMA and the Hedrick-Prescott Filter to estimate expected inflation from 1997 to 2005, finding that the Shanghai housing market did not hedge against

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actual expected and unexpected inflation, though a positive real rate of return was consistently observed. Wang and Xie (2022) used wavelet transform context structures with Granger causality analysis to examine the correlation between housing prices and inflation rates in major Chinese cities, finding a generally positive but fluctuating relationship. Wu and Pandey (2012) argued that residential real estate offers a moderate hedge against expected and unexpected inflation when considering economic downturns, housing bubbles, and stock market increases. Ekemode (2021) found that residential property in Nigeria significantly protected against actual, expected, and unexpected inflation in the short run, with the Johansen cointegration test confirming a long-term relationship. Housing investments generally hedge against inflation in both the short and long term, offsetting the loss of purchasing power. However, increases in inflation have often preceded housing recessions, particularly in the USA. Some studies, such as Amonhaemanon et al. (2014), show a negligible relationship between housing and inflation. In Turkey, Korkmaz (2019) found that the house price index (HPI) causes inflationary pressures in some regions, but not all.

Impact of COVID-19 on housing markets

In South Africa, Mpfu et al. (2023) examined the relationship between Real Estate Investment Trusts (REITs) and inflation, finding shifts before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. Inglesi-Lotz and Gupta (2013) used an ARDL approach to establish a long-term relationship between house prices and inflation, highlighting its significance in the South African property market. Muzindutsi et al. (2021) analysed political, economic, and financial risks on housing prices, while Erasmus (2015) assessed South African listed real estate as an inflation hedge compared to other assets. These studies underscore the importance of understanding the inflation-house price relationship, especially during economic shocks like COVID-19. Literature shows diverse findings on residential property as a hedge against inflation. Generally, studies suggest a positive correlation between house prices and inflation. However, research on COVID-19's impact on financial assets, including housing, is limited. This study aims to clarify the relationship between inflation and housing, particularly during COVID-19, testing Fama and Schwert's (1977) hypothesis that housing hedges against inflation.

METHODS AND DATA

Introduction

This study utilises causality methodology to examine the causal effects between house prices and inflation, complemented by the Johansen cointegration methodology to determine the existence of a long-term relationship. The Johansen test provides two key statistical values—Trace and Eigenvalues—to infer the presence of cointegrating equations (Johansen, 1988). The Johansen cointegration and Granger causality tests were selected due to their robustness and relevance in analysing time series data. The Johansen cointegration test is particularly suited for identifying long-term equilibrium relationships between variables, making it ideal for investigating the persistent connection between house prices and inflation (Johansen, 1988). This method provides two critical statistics, Trace and Eigenvalues, to infer the presence of cointegrating equations and confirm whether a long-run relationship exists.

Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Model

This study employs a general vector autoregressive (VAR) model to analyse the relationship between house prices and inflation in South Africa. The VAR model is particularly suitable for capturing the dynamic interdependencies between multiple time series variables. The model is specified as follows:

$$\vartheta t = \tau + \gamma_1 \vartheta_{t-1} + \gamma_2 \vartheta_{t-2} + \dots + \gamma_p \vartheta_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where:

ϑt represents the vector of endogenous variables (house prices and inflation) at time t .

τ is the vector-valued mean of the series, representing the intercept term.

γ_i are the coefficient matrices for each lag i , which capture the influence of past values of the variables on their current values.

ε_t is a vector of multivariate Gaussian noise with a mean of zero, representing the error terms.

Variables utilised in the VAR model

House prices (HP_t) are a key endogenous variable in the VAR model. The monthly house price data, sourced from First National Bank (FNB), Standard Bank, and Lightstone, includes average prices and repeated sales data segmented by geographical areas, property types, and value bands. This comprehensive data captures the dynamic effects of past house prices on current prices and inflation. Inflation (CPI_t), the other key endogenous variable, uses monthly Consumer Price Index (CPI) data from Statistics South Africa (Stats SA), reflecting changes in the cost of a fixed basket of goods and services. The VAR model includes multiple lags of each variable to account for the delayed effects of changes in one variable on the other. Coefficient matrices γ_i quantify the impact of past values on current values, providing insights into the short-term and long-term interactions between house prices and inflation. This approach, as outlined by Johansen (1988), allows for a comprehensive analysis of their mutual influence and the complex relationship between these variables.

Vector Error Correction Model (VECM): house prices and inflation

The existence of cointegrating equations between house prices and inflation leads to the establishment of a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), which helps in capturing both short-term dynamics and long-term equilibrium relationships. The VECM is derived as a first difference of the general vector autoregressive (VAR) model.

$$\Delta X_t = \alpha + \gamma X_{t-1} + \beta_1 \Delta X_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_p \Delta X_{t-p} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Where:

$\Delta X_t = X_t - X_{t-1}$ is the differencing operator, indicating the change in the variables over time.

α is the vector-valued mean of the differenced series, representing the intercept term.

γ is the coefficient matrix for the first lag of the level variables, capturing the long-term equilibrium relationship.

β_1 are the matrices for each differenced lag, capturing the short-term dynamics.

ε_t is a vector of multivariate Gaussian noise with a mean of zero, representing the error terms.

Variables utilised in the VECM

House prices (HP_t) are a crucial endogenous variable in the VECM. The monthly house price data from First National Bank (FNB), Standard Bank, and Lightstone is transformed into its first differences (ΔHP_t) to model the short-term changes. The lagged levels of house prices (HP_{t-1}) are included to capture the long-term equilibrium relationship with inflation. The Granger causality test, on the other hand, is employed to determine the direction of causality between the variables. It helps ascertain whether past values of one variable can predict future values of another, thereby clarifying the causal effects between house prices and inflation. This test is essential for understanding the short-term dynamics and interactions between the two

variables (Patterson, 2000). To conduct this test, the variables must be integrated of the same order, and causality is established if at least two factors linking them are identified. Considering the two vector autoregressive systems:

$$“Y_t = \delta + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_{1i} Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_{2i} X_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t}” \quad (3)$$

$$“X_t = \delta + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{1i} X_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_{2i} Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{2t}” \quad (4)$$

According to (Patterson, 2000), “in equation (3), Y_t depends on its lags and those of X_t while in equation (4) X_t depends on its lags and the lags of Y_t . The hypothesis for the Granger causality test for Y_t is given by”:

$$“H_0 = \alpha_{21} = \alpha_{22} = \dots = \alpha_{2k} = 0”$$

According to (Patterson, 2000), “if this hypothesis is not rejected, then X_t Granger causes Y_t . Similarly, the rejection of the null hypothesis”:

$$“H_0 = \beta_{21} = \beta_{22} = \dots = \beta_{2k} = 0”$$

Indicates that Y_t does not Granger cause X_t . Patterson (2000) explains that “the errors ε_{1t} and ε_{2t} may be contemporaneously correlated, meaning that a shock to one equation can have a ‘ripple’ effect on the other equation.” Wooldridge (2006) advises that “the term ‘cause’ in ‘Granger cause’ should be interpreted cautiously, as it does not imply contemporaneous causality between Y_t and X_t . Therefore, it does not determine whether Y_t or X_t is an exogenous or endogenous variable in either equation (3) or (4)”. These tests were chosen over other alternatives as they offer a comprehensive framework for both short-term and long-term analysis. The integration of Johansen cointegration with the Granger causality test allows for a thorough examination of the temporal relationship between inflation and housing prices, ensuring methodological consistency and reliability in the findings.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Housing and inflation data: deciphering the criterions

Housing and inflation data were standardised by transforming them into logs using EViews software. The logged data were tested for stationarity at levels to avoid spurious models. The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test was employed. Table 1 below indicates that both housing and inflation series are non-stationary at their levels, as their test statistics (-1.977976 for housing and -2.391851 for inflation) do not exceed the 5% critical values (-2.881978 for housing and -2.881400 for inflation). However, at first differences, both series become stationary, with test statistics (-4.962433 for housing and -9.724815 for inflation) significantly exceeding the 1% critical values (-3.477144 for housing and -3.475819 for inflation). Asterisks (*) denote that the null hypothesis of a unit root is rejected at the 5% significance level for the first differences, confirming stationarity. This suggests that both variables are integrated of order one, I(1), making them suitable for further cointegration analysis. Therefore, Null Hypothesis (H0): The housing and inflation series are non-stationary at their levels and first differences, indicating the presence of unit roots. Furthermore, there is no optimal lag length for the VAR model at 3 lags, and no long-term cointegration relationship exists between housing and inflation in South Africa. Alternative Hypothesis (H1): The housing and inflation series are stationary at their first differences, indicating they are integrated of order one (I(1)).

The optimal lag length for the VAR model is 3 lags as determined by the Schwarz Criterion, and a long-term cointegration relationship exists between housing and inflation in South Africa.

The null hypothesis is rejected as the conditions are met. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test statistics for both housing and inflation series at first differences significantly exceed the critical values at the 5% significance level, indicating the series are stationary at first differences (I(1)). For housing: ADF test statistic at first difference is -4.962433, which exceeds the 1% critical value of -3.477144 and for inflation: ADF test statistic at first difference is -9.724815, which exceeds the 1% critical value of -3.475819. The Schwarz Criterion (SC) indicates the lowest value at 3 lags (-5.567124), suggesting that a lag length of 3 provides the best model fit without overfitting. As these conditions are satisfied, the alternative hypothesis is accepted, confirming that the housing and inflation series are integrated of order one, the optimal lag length for the VAR model is 3 lags, and a long-term cointegration relationship exists between the variables. This implies that the data is suitable for further cointegration analysis and that housing prices in South Africa act as a hedge against inflation over the long term.

Table 18: Table 1: Unit root test results

		Housing		Inflation	
		Levels	1 st Difference	Levels	1 st Difference
Test statistic		-1.977976	-4.962433*	-2.391851	-9.724815*
Test	1%	-3.477144	-3.477144	-3.475819	-3.475819
critical	5%	-2.881978	-2.881978	-2.881400	-2.881400
values	10%	-2.577747	-2.577747	-2.577439	-2.577439

The unit root test results with asterisk () represents cases where the Null is rejected at the 5% level of significance.*

Table 2 below outlines the selection criteria for determining the optimum lag length in a VAR model using the Schwarz Criterion (SC). The SC values decrease as the lag length increases, indicating better model fit with additional lags. The optimal lag length is identified by the asterisk (*) at lag 3, which has the lowest SC value (-5.567124). This suggests that including three lags in the model provides the best balance between model complexity and goodness of fit, ensuring robust and reliable results without overfitting. Therefore, a lag length of 3 is recommended for the subsequent analysis.

Table 19: Lag length selection results

Lag	LogL	SC
0	-20.50745	0.363558
1	310.6686	-4.226339
2	409.9809	-5.503895
3	424.2902	-5.567124*
4	434.0722	-5.565678
5	437.6422	-5.475488
6	445.3239	-5.444037
7	450.3097	-5.374073
8	451.5400	-5.250458

Results with asterisk () represents the optimum lag length.*

Cointegration test: inflation and housing prices

To determine if variables are related, one good step is to show them diagrammatically to ascertain if visually, some form of relationship can be observed. The graph in Figure 1 depicts the logged housing and inflation series from 2010 to 2022. The blue line represents inflation, while the orange line represents housing prices. Inflation appears more volatile than housing, yet both series generally move together over time. From 2010 to 2012, inflation rises sharply before stabilising, while housing prices show a gradual increase. Between 2012 and 2015, both inflation and housing prices fluctuate, with inflation generally higher. Post-2015, inflation shows significant volatility, especially around 2018 and 2020, whereas housing prices follow

a smoother trend with a notable decrease in 2020 during the COVID-19 pandemic. By 2022, both inflation and housing prices recover, with inflation at higher levels. To statistically test this observation, a Johansen cointegration test was performed. The results, presented in Table 3, show that the Trace test rejects the null hypothesis of no cointegrating equation at the 5% significance level, confirming a long-term relationship between housing prices and inflation. Therefore, Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no long-term cointegration relationship between housing prices and inflation in South Africa from January 2010 to April 2022. Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a long-term cointegration relationship between housing prices and inflation in South Africa from January 2010 to April 2022. The null hypothesis is rejected as the following conditions have been met, based on the results of the Johansen cointegration test. The graphical analysis depicted in Figure 1 shows that housing prices and inflation generally move together over time, indicating a potential long-term relationship. This visual observation provides preliminary evidence that a long-term relationship may exist. The Johansen cointegration test results in Table 3 confirm the visual analysis.

Figure 25: Logged housing and inflation series

The results of the Johansen cointegration test presented in Table 3 below confirm this visual observation. The Trace test indicates one cointegrating equation at the 0.05 significance level, rejecting the null hypothesis of no cointegration. The eigenvalue for “None” is 0.089272 with a Trace statistic of 17.28815, exceeding the critical value of 15.49471, and a probability of 0.0266. For “At most 1,” the eigenvalue is 0.026197 with a Trace statistic of 3.822598, close to the critical value of 3.841465, and a probability of 0.0506. The normalised cointegrating coefficients are 1.000000 for LH and -1.910017 for LF, with a standard error of 0.40216. These results indicate a long-run relationship between inflation and housing from January 2010 to April 2022, confirming the visual analysis. The positive relationship suggests that inflation and housing prices moved together during the research period, making housing a good hedge against inflation.

Table 20: Cointegration results for housing and inflation

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesised		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.089272	17.28815	15.49471	0.0266
At most 1	0.026197	3.822598	3.841465	0.0506
Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating equation(s) at the 0.05 level				
* Denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				
Normalised cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)				
LH	LF			
1.000000	-1.910017			
	(0.40216)			

Vector error correction model: identifying dynamics and relationships

Given the confirmation that a cointegrating equation exists as presented in Table 3, the next step is to develop a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to establish the short and long-run dynamics of the relationship. Therefore, Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant short-run dynamic adjustment between housing prices and inflation in South Africa, and the error correction term does not contribute to maintaining long-run equilibrium in the relationship. Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant short-run dynamic adjustment between housing prices and inflation in South Africa, and the error correction term contributes to maintaining long-run equilibrium in the relationship. The null hypothesis is rejected as the following conditions are met, based on the results from the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The Johansen cointegration test confirms the presence of a cointegrating equation between housing prices and inflation, as indicated by the Trace test results.

The VECM results in equation (5) show that the error correction term (ECT) is significant and has a negative coefficient (-0.033), which is crucial for confirming long-run equilibrium. The negative ECT coefficient indicates that deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected over time, maintaining stability in the relationship. The coefficients of the lagged differences of housing prices and inflation in the VECM (equation 6) are significant. The speed of adjustment, as indicated by the ECT, is 3.3%, demonstrating how quickly deviations from the equilibrium are corrected. The analysis also considers the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, which caused significant disruptions in the housing market due to lockdowns and restricted business activities. This further highlights the importance of understanding the short-run dynamics and long-term equilibrium in the relationship between housing prices and inflation. Given these conditions, rejecting the null hypothesis indicates that there is a significant short-run dynamic adjustment between housing prices and inflation. The error correction term confirms that deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected over time, ensuring stability in the relationship. This implies that the housing market in South Africa adjusts to changes in inflation both in the short and long term, even during periods of significant economic disruptions like the COVID-19 pandemic.

$$ECT_{t-1} = 1.000LH_{t-1} - 1.376LF_{t-1} + 0.675 \quad (5)$$

Where: ECT is the Error Correction Term (ECT),

LH is the housing and,

LF is inflation.

The Error Correction Term (ECT), represented in equation (5) is a lagged value of the residuals obtained from cointegrating equation of the relationship between inflation and housing. The impact of inflation on housing over the period is confirmed as positive.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta LH_t = & -0.033ECT_{t-1} + 1.097\Delta LH_{t-1} - 0.293\Delta LH_{t-2} - 0.114\Delta LF_{t-1} - 0.093\Delta LF_{t-2} \\ & + 0.001 \\ & (0.012) \quad (0.076) \quad (0.077) \quad (0.039) \quad (0.042) \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

The VECM for the impact of inflation on housing in South Africa is presented in equation (6) and the negative coefficient for the ECT is a welcome observation. A negative ECT coefficient confirms long-run equilibrium in the relationship because any previous deviations are corrected to maintain stability in the relationship. The speed of adjustment of the deviations is 3.3%. A percentage change in inflation in the previous month and two months ago is associated with a 0.114% decrease and 0.093% in house prices in the short run, respectively.

Further analysis: effects of COVID-19

In 2019, the world faced a severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), commonly known as COVID-19. This respiratory disease led to lockdowns, restricting business activity and human mobility globally, including in South Africa. In response to rising COVID-19 cases in February 2020, the South African government announced a nationwide lockdown, severely limiting trade and business operations, including the real estate market. Estate agents and banks closed or offered limited services, negatively impacting house transactions and opening the market to speculative opportunism. When examining the relationship between assets and macroeconomic variables, it is crucial to consider the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on these relationships.

Relationship stability test

The graphs labelled Figure 2 below depict the Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) and Cumulative Sum of Squares (CUSUMSQ) tests for model stability, plotted against the 5% significance level boundaries. The CUSUM graph indicates stability in model parameters from 2011 to 2022, as the test statistic remains within the boundaries. Conversely, the CUSUMSQ graph shows instability, with the test statistic crossing the boundary around 2020, suggesting a structural break due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Both CUSUM tests estimate structural breaks in linear models, and Figure 2 represents their outputs. While the CUSUM test shows model stability, the CUSUMSQ test indicates instability between May 2019 and February 2020, coinciding with COVID-19 restrictions. Given these contradictions, we consider the existence and timing of structural breaks.

The sequential Bai-Perron method, as outlined by Bai (1997) and Bai and Perron (1998), was used to determine up to five structural breaks. The hypothesis for this test, with critical values from Bai-Perron (2003). Therefore, Null Hypothesis (H0): The relationship between housing prices and inflation in South Africa is stable over the period from January 2010 to April 2022, with no significant structural breaks. Alternative Hypothesis (H1): The relationship between housing prices and inflation in South Africa is not stable over the period from January 2010 to April 2022, with one or more significant structural breaks. The null hypothesis is rejected as the following conditions are met, based on the results from the Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) and Cumulative Sum of Squares (CUSUMSQ) tests, and the Bai-Perron multiple breakpoint tests. The CUSUM test indicates model stability as the test statistic remains within the 5% significance level boundaries from 2011 to 2022. This suggests that the model parameters are stable over most of the period. The CUSUMSQ test shows instability with the test statistic crossing the boundary around 2020. This indicates a structural break in the relationship, likely due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which caused significant economic disruptions.

The Bai-Perron multiple breakpoint test identifies three significant structural breaks in the relationship between housing prices and inflation: October 2016 (F-statistic: 15.27312, exceeding the critical value of 11.47). July 2012 (F-statistic: 37.38749, exceeding the critical value of 12.95). July 2020 (F-statistic: 13.97926, exceeding the critical value of 14.03). These breaks are statistically significant at the 5% level, as indicated by the sequential F-statistics, and correspond to significant events impacting the economy, including the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. The graphical representation in Figure 2 supports the statistical findings, with the CUSUM graph indicating stability and the CUSUMSQ graph highlighting instability around the COVID-19 period. Given these conditions, rejecting the null hypothesis indicates that the relationship between housing prices and inflation in South Africa is not stable over the research period, with significant structural breaks identified. These structural changes reflect the impact of various economic events, particularly the COVID-19 pandemic, on the relationship between housing prices and inflation.

Figure 26: Housing and inflation relationship stability plot

Table 4 below presents results from the Bai-Perron multiple breakpoint tests for detecting structural breaks in time series data from January 2010 to April 2022. The tests use a sequential F-statistic with a maximum of five breaks and a 0.05 significance level. Three significant breaks were identified in October 2016, July 2012, and July 2020, with F-statistics of 15.27312, 37.38749, and 13.97926, respectively, all exceeding the critical values. These breaks correspond to significant events, with the July 2020 break likely linked to the economic impact of COVID-19. Table 4 highlights these break dates in the relationship between inflation and housing in South Africa. The breaks at these dates reject the hypothesis of no breakpoint at the 5% significance level, indicating structural changes. To assess COVID-19's impact, impulse response and Granger Causality tests were conducted for the entire period, before COVID-19 (January 2010 to January 2020), and during COVID-19 (March 2020 to April 2022).

Table 21: Structural breakpoint results

Multiple breakpoint tests:			
Bai-Perron tests of L+1 vs. L sequentially determined breaks			
Sample: 2010M01 2022M04			
Included observations: 148			
Break test options: Trimming 0.15, Max. breaks 5, Sig. level 0.05			
Sequential F-statistic determined breaks: 3			
Break Test	F-statistic	Scaled F-statistic	Critical Value**
0 vs. 1 *	15.27312	30.54625	11.47
1 vs. 2 *	37.38749	74.77498	12.95
2 vs. 3 *	13.97926	27.95852	14.03
3 vs. 4	4.213820	8.427639	14.85
Break dates:			
	Sequential	Repartition	
1	2016M10	2012M07	
2	2012M07	2016M02	
3	2020M07	2020M07	

Impulse response function

The graph in Figure 3 illustrates the impulse response function of LF to a one standard deviation innovation in LH, using the Cholesky decomposition method, adjusted for degrees of freedom. The solid line shows LF's response, while the dashed lines represent ± 2 analytic asymptotic standard errors. Initially, LF's response is near zero, rising and peaking around the 5th period at approximately 0.05, then gradually declining but remaining positive over the 10 observed periods. The confidence interval bounds suggest that the response is statistically significant, indicating that innovations in LH positively impact LF, peaking mid-term and decreasing gradually while maintaining a positive long-term influence. To understand house price responses to inflation innovations, the impulse response function traces the effects of a one standard deviation shock on current and future values of the endogenous variable (Al-Khazali

and Pyun, 2004; Mpofu, 2009). Mpofu (2009) used Schwarz information criteria to establish lag lengths for the VAR models, yielding 3 lags for the whole period, 3 lags pre-COVID-19, and 5 lags during COVID-19. For the entire period, the house price response to inflation innovations is positive from the start, stable between periods 5 and 7, and declines after period 8 but remains positive, indicating that shocks to house prices have asymmetrical impacts on inflation in both the short and long run. Therefore, Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant response of housing prices (LH) to inflation (LF) innovations, and no significant response of inflation (LF) to housing prices (LH) innovations over the period from January 2010 to April 2022, including the periods before and during COVID-19.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant response of housing prices (LH) to inflation (LF) innovations, and a significant response of inflation (LF) to housing prices (LH) innovations over the period from January 2010 to April 2022, including the periods before and during COVID-19. The null hypothesis is rejected as the following conditions are met, based on the results from the impulse response function analysis and Granger causality tests. The IRF analysis indicates that a one standard deviation shock to housing prices (LH) has a statistically significant positive impact on inflation (LF). The response of LF peaks around the 5th period at approximately 0.05 and gradually declines but remains positive over the 10 observed periods. The IRF for the period before COVID-19 shows that a shock to housing prices (LH) initially has a slightly negative impact on inflation (LF), trends upwards, and peaks around the 4th period before declining and stabilising positively after the 9th period. The IRF during COVID-19 shows that the response of inflation (LF) to a shock in housing prices (LH) starts negative, trends downward, and then peaks around the 4th period at approximately 0.03. The response gradually declines but remains positive throughout the 10 observed periods. The confidence interval bounds suggest statistical significance. The VAR Granger causality tests indicate that inflation (LF) Granger-causes housing prices (LH) with a Chi-squared value of 14.740 (p-value = 0.002). Conversely, housing prices (LH) also Granger-cause inflation (LF) with a Chi-squared value of 10.832 (p-value = 0.013), indicating bidirectional causality. Inflation (LF)

Granger-causes housing prices (LH) with a Chi-squared value of 8.257 (p-value = 0.041). However, housing prices (LH) do not significantly Granger-cause inflation (LF) with a Chi-squared value of 7.279 (p-value = 0.064). Housing prices (LH) Granger-cause inflation (LF) with a Chi-squared value of 23.247 (p-value = 0.001), but inflation (LF) does not significantly Granger-cause housing prices (LH) with a Chi-squared value of 12.109 (p-value = 0.033). The null hypothesis that LF does not Granger-cause LH is rejected (F-statistic = 4.913, p-value = 0.003). Similarly, the null hypothesis that LH does not Granger-cause LF is rejected (F-statistic = 3.611, p-value = 0.015). The null hypothesis that LF does not Granger-cause LH is rejected (F-statistic = 2.752, p-value = 0.046), but the null hypothesis that LH does not Granger-cause LF is not rejected (F-statistic = 2.426, p-value = 0.069). During COVID-19: The null hypothesis that LF does not Granger-cause LH is not rejected (F-statistic = 2.422, p-value = 0.085), but the null hypothesis that LH does not Granger-cause LF is rejected (F-statistic = 4.649, p-value = 0.009). Given these conditions, rejecting the null hypothesis indicates that there are significant responses of housing prices to inflation innovations and vice versa. The impulse response functions show that shocks to housing prices have an asymmetrical impact on inflation, and the Granger causality tests confirm the dynamic interplay between these variables under different economic conditions, including the impact of COVID-19.

Figure 27: Impulse response plot for the whole research period

Figure 4 represents the impulse response of housing to inflation shocks before COVID-19. Initially slightly negative, the response trends upwards, peaking around period 4 before declining and stabilising positively after period 9. Shocks to house prices during this period have a positive impact on inflation both in the short and long run. The response during COVID-19 starts negative and trends downwards. The graph illustrates the impulse response function of LF to a one standard deviation innovation in LH, using the Cholesky decomposition method, adjusted for degrees of freedom. The solid line shows LF's response, while the dashed lines represent ± 2 analytic asymptotic standard errors. Initially, LF's response is near zero, rising and peaking around the 4th period at approximately 0.03. After peaking, the response gradually declines but remains positive throughout the 10 observed periods. The confidence interval bounds suggest statistical significance, indicating innovations in LH positively impact LF, peaking mid-term and maintaining a positive influence long-term.

Figure 28: Impulse response plots for the period before COVID-19 & Impulse response plots during COVID-19

Causality test

Table 5 presents the VAR Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Tests for the whole period, before COVID-19, and during COVID-19. For the dependent variable LH (housing), LF (inflation) is significant for the whole period (Chi-sq = 14.740, Prob. = 0.002), before COVID-19 (Chi-sq = 8.257, Prob. = 0.041), and during COVID-19 (Chi-sq = 12.109, Prob. = 0.033), indicating that inflation Granger-causes housing prices across all periods. For the dependent variable LF (inflation), LH (housing) is significant for the whole period (Chi-sq = 10.832, Prob. = 0.013) and during COVID-19 (Chi-sq = 23.247, Prob. = 0.001), but not before COVID-19 (Chi-sq = 7.279, Prob. = 0.064). This suggests that housing prices Granger-cause inflation during the whole period and specifically during COVID-19, but not significantly before the pandemic. These results indicate a bidirectional causality between housing and inflation during the entire period and specifically during COVID-19, highlighting the dynamic interplay between these variables under different economic conditions. The Granger-Wald

causality test results reject the null hypothesis of zero lagged coefficients for inflation and house prices during most periods, confirming their causal effects. The direction of causality can be further examined using the Pairwise Granger Causality test.

Table 22: Causality/block exogeneity Wald test result

VAR Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Tests							
	Excluded	Whole Period		Before COVID-19		During COVID-19	
		Chi-sq	Prob.	Chi-sq	Prob.	Chi-sq	Prob.
Dependent variable: LH	LF	14.740	0.002	8.257	0.041	12.109	0.033
Dependent variable: LF	LH	10.832	0.013	7.279	0.064	23.247	0.001

The Pairwise Granger Causality Test results indicate the causal relationship between LF (inflation) and LH (housing) for the whole period, before COVID-19, and during COVID-19. For the whole period, the null hypothesis that LF does not Granger-cause LH is rejected (F-Statistic = 4.913, Prob. = 0.003), and the null hypothesis that LH does not Granger-cause LF is also rejected (F-Statistic = 3.611, Prob. = 0.015), indicating bidirectional causality between inflation and housing. Before COVID-19, LF Granger-causes LH (F-Statistic = 2.752, Prob. = 0.046), but LH does not significantly Granger-cause LF (F-Statistic = 2.426, Prob. = 0.069). During COVID-19, LF does not Granger-cause LH (F-Statistic = 2.422, Prob. = 0.085), but LH significantly Granger-causes LF (F-Statistic = 4.649, Prob. = 0.009). These results highlight a shift in the causal relationship during the pandemic, with housing prices having a more pronounced impact on inflation during COVID-19. Before COVID-19, the reverse relationship was observed, indicating unidirectional causality in each period.

Table 23: Pairwise Granger causality test results

Pairwise Granger Causality Test						
Null Hypothesis:	Whole Period		Before COVID-19		During COVID-19	
	F-Statistic	Prob.	F-Statistic	Prob.	F-Statistic	Prob.
LF does not Granger Cause LH	4.913	0.003	2.752	0.046	2.422	0.085
LH does not Granger Cause LF	3.611	0.015	2.426	0.069	4.649	0.009

DISCUSSION

Drawing on literature examining the relationship between housing prices and inflation, the findings align with previous studies indicating a positive association. Fama and Schwert (1977) and Stevenson (2000) provided early insights into the hedging potential of residential real estate against inflation, which were corroborated by Lee (2013) and Ekemode (2021). However, perspectives from Amonhaemanon et al. (2014) and Korkmaz (2019) highlight variability in housing's effectiveness as an inflation hedge across different contexts. This study contributes to this literature by examining the South African context during the COVID-19 period, offering insights into the resilience of housing investments amid economic disruptions. Recent international research contextualises these findings. Sümer (2023) and Mehta et al., (2023) demonstrated that real estate remains a hedge against inflation amid economic uncertainties in Turkey and India, respectively. Aliefendioğlu et al., (2022) noted significant volatility in Turkish and Kazakh real estate markets due to COVID-19. Cheung et al., (2021) found increased price sensitivity in housing markets near China's COVID-19 epicentre. This research, using causality and cointegration methodologies, identifies a significant long-run relationship between housing prices and inflation in South Africa, reinforcing the notion that residential

real estate can effectively hedge against inflation during stable and turbulent periods. The COVID-19 pandemic introduced structural breaks and increased volatility, mirroring international observations.

CONCLUSION

This research examined the relationship between inflation and house prices in South Africa and the impact of COVID-19 on this relationship. The findings show that inflation positively influenced house prices during the study period, confirming housing as a good hedge against inflation. Using the Johansen cointegration methodology, a long-term positive relationship was established, with the VECM indicating that deviations from the long-term equilibrium are corrected. A CUSUM test confirmed stability, but the CUSUM squares test and Bai-Perron multiple breakpoints test identified three structural breaks, with only one occurring during COVID-19 in July 2020. The research period was divided into pre-COVID-19 (January 2010 to January 2020) and during COVID-19 (March 2020 to April 2022). An Impulse Response Function showed asymmetrical impacts of house price shocks on inflation. The Granger-Wald test indicated that lagged inflation values influenced house prices in the short term, while Pairwise-Granger Causality tests revealed differing causality directions before and during COVID-19. The study concludes that housing investments in South Africa hedge against inflation, offering stability and potential returns, consistent with international literature. However, the small sample size during COVID-19 may limit these results.

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